

Screening wheat varieties for being used as allelopathic crops in sustainable agriculture. The role of allelochemical compounds

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This study focuses on the potential benefits of screening allelopathic cultivars for sustainable weed management. The allelopathic potential of 30 wheat cultivars grown with two aggressive and herbicide-resistant weeds, the dicotyledonous common purslane (*Portulaca oleracea* L.) and the monocotyledonous annual ryegrass (*Lolium rigidum* Gaud), was evaluated to see how different varieties could affect each weed differently. After co-culture of wheat cultivars with the weeds, germination rate (GR), plant weight (PW), shoot and root length (SL and RL), and plant height (PH) of the weeds were measured to obtain information about the reduction or stimulation of shoot and root growth, the ability of weed species to colonise and occupy the space through germination and development (Shoot Invasive Capacity (SIC) and Root Invasive Capacity (RIC)) and how weed plants can develop in next generation (Seedling Vigour Index (SVI)). SL, RL and PW of each wheat variety were also measured. Moreover, allelochemicals from shoots, roots, and root exudates from wheat were quantified to evaluate the accumulation or release of these compounds by the different wheat accessions in front of the weeds. A correlation was found between root exudation and weed inhibition. For example, the large amount of root exudates of Ursita resulted in a strong inhibition of both weeds. The same was true for Maurizio and Midas, which exuded higher amounts of benzoxazinoids than other varieties, resulting in weaker and smaller weeds. By contrary, accumulation of phenolic compounds in the plant organs without exudation to the medium suggests a defensive or protecting role of these compounds more than an allelochemical role. Moreover, the weed pressure influences also the amount of compounds exuded by the roots to the media, which supports the idea of promoting biodiversity in agroecological systems. Regarding *L. rigidum* and *P. oleracea* management, the most promising varieties for controlling annual ryegrass are NS Azra, Ludwig, Maurizio, PS Dobromila, Midas and Tobias, while Capo, Glosa, Adesso, Annie, Ludwig, Midas and NS Azra were the most phytotoxic against common purslane. In summary, this study reveals that variety screening is crucial to move towards sustainable weed management and agroecological farming.

Acknowledgements: This project was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 771367 and by the Horizon Europe project (HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-02-01) AGROSUS: AGROecological strategies for SUStainable weed management in key European crops. Proposal ID: 101084084.

Keywords: allelopathic crops, wheat, biological control, allelochemicals, agroecological farming

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